

ANALYSIS OF IN-HOSPITAL COMPLICATIONS AFTER PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION (PCI) OF CULPRIT VESSEL FOR ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME

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Abstract:

Introduction: Acute coronary syndrome is a term used for any condition brought on by sudden, reduced blood flow to the heart. Acute coronary syndrome depends on the specific characteristics of each element of the triad of clinical presentation (including a history of coronary artery disease). **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyze the in-hospital complications after Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) of culprit vessel for Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS). **Materials and methods:** This descriptive case series study was conducted at Sheikh Zayed Medical College Raheem Yar Khan during 2018 to 2019. It was non-probability purposive sampling. All the baseline procedural and biochemical characteristics recorded. Frequency of males and females undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel during this duration was calculated then these patients were evaluated for Post PCI Complications. **Results:** Males were more in number as compared to females. i.e 75 males (55.55%) and 60 females (44.44%). Out of these 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) were selected for this study. These patients were fulfilling the Inclusion and exclusion criteria. Baseline characteristics of the patients who underwent PCI are shown below in table 1. Mean age of the male patients was 49.8 ± 9.60 while that of female patients was 52.1 ± 8.91 . **Conclusion:** It is the total obstruction of the artery usually at the site of access requiring surgical repair. Conclusion is defined as total obstruction of blood vessel usually due to the thrombus formation dissection or other mechanisms usually at the site of access of plaque pulse or Doppler signal and associated with sign and symptoms of an ischemic limb requiring surgical intervention.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute coronary syndrome is a term used for any condition brought on by sudden, reduced blood flow to the heart. Acute coronary syndrome depends on the specific characteristics of each element of the triad of clinical presentation (including a history of coronary artery disease). The prevalence of the ACS ranged from 7.8% to 32.2%. The number of PCI is increasing with the passage of time due to increased awareness and improved outcomes compared to fibrinolytic therapy for coronary artery disease (CAD)¹. Meta- analyses of randomized clinical trials have reported that primary PCI is more cost effective compared to fibrinolytic and reduces the incidence of death, reinfarction and stroke. Furthermore in stable patients and in patients with multi vessel disease, PCI has become the preferred procedure in the United States with declining mortality in patients undergoing multi vessel PCI². PCI also has got many complications like other interventions i.e Death, myocardial infarction (MI), emergency CABG or re do PCI ,stroke ,contrast induced nephropathy (CIN) Vascular complications before intervention³. GpIIb/IIIa inhibitors have reduced the mortality by 20% over 6-12 months in unstable angina and non ST elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI). PCI has not shown any mortality benefit in stable angina. Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in women. Sex based differences has been area of active investigation over the past two decades⁴. Symptoms of females appear at elder age as compare to male, however the symptoms of females are atypical as compare to males. The diagnosis is more difficult in females and prognosis is less favorable⁵. It has reported in several studies that female undergo intervention less frequently as compare to males. PCI on females is usually is usually more complicated due to gender related small sized coronary arteries⁶. Thus females are at more risk of post PCI complications and also at increased risk of mortality and morbidity⁷.

OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the study is to analyze the in-hospital complications after Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) of culprit vessel for Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This descriptive case series study was conducted at Sheikh Zayed Medical College Raheem Yar Khan

during 2018 to 2019. It was non-probability purposive sampling. All the baseline procedural and biochemical characteristics recorded. Frequency of males and females undergoing PCI of Culprit Vessel during this duration was calculated then these patients were evaluated for Post PCI Complications. These patients were admitted to hospital with ACS. These patients received Primary, Rescue and facilitated PCI. 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) out of these 135 patients were selected. Written consent was taken before starting the study protocol. Detail History with demographic features was taken and patients were divided in two groups on the basis of gender. Risk factors were also stratified i.e

- Diabetes Mellitus (fasting blood sugar >126 mg/dl and Random >200 mg/dl)
- Hypertension (sustained elevation in blood pressure of >140/80 or previous history) and smoking.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS (statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 12 for window. Continuous (Age, BMI) and Categorical variables (Gender, procedural complications i.e CIN, Hematoma, MI. etc), were presented as mean± standard deviation and frequency/percentages respectively.

RESULTS:

Males were more in number as compared to females. i.e 75 males (55.55%) and 60 females (44.44%). Out of these 110 patients (55 males and 55 females) were selected for this study. These patients were fulfilling the Inclusion and exclusion criteria. Baseline characteristics of the patients who underwent PCI are shown below in table 1. Mean age of the male patients was 49.8 ± 9.60 while that of female patients was 52.1 ± 8.91 .

Out of 525 male patients who underwent PCI, 21% of the patients were diabetics. Hypertension was present in 46% of the male patients. Among the female patients the incidence of diabetes and hypertension was 29% and 53% respectively. The mean body mass index (BMI) of female patients was also higher than the male patients i.e 30.2 vs 28.6 respectively.

TABLE 01 .Indications for PCI

	Male(55)	Female(55)
Acute Myocardial Infarction (primary)	14.54%(8)	5.45%(3)
Acute Myocardial Infarction(rescue)	5.45%(3)	3.63%(2)
Acute Myocardial Infarction (elective)	41.81%(23)	56.36(31)
NSTEMI	27.27%(15)	25.45%(14)
Unstable Angina	10.90%(6)	9.09%(5)

Characteristics of the procedure are shown here

DISCUSSION:

Main function of heart is to provide circulatory needs of the body. Heart also need its own metabolic requirements. These requirements are met through the coronary blood flow. Heart needs aerobic metabolism, there is limited capacity of heart to tolerate anaerobic metabolism. Heart has a unique mechanism of oxygen extraction. Under basal condition it extract high degree of oxygen so that it can adjust a changing oxygen needs by only a small increment in oxygen extraction⁸. There is more coronary blood flow if there's more need of oxygen to the cardiac muscle. To measure the oxygen consumption by cardiac muscle certain studies have been done on animals⁹. It is very difficult to calculate the mean myocardial oxygen consumptions (MVO₂) there is laboratory data that can be used to measure MVO₂. To meet the bad time heart has sufficient reservoir of oxygen¹⁰.

Oxygen consumption correlated with the tension time index only until the peak systolic pressure had been attained at which 91% of oxygen consumption per beat had occurred. Oxygen consumption is not uniform throughout the systole (tension time index). It is due to the insensitivity to the duration of pressure maintenance between peak systolic pressure and the end of relaxation. Wall stress is more related to MVO₂¹¹.

CONCLUSION:

It is the total obstruction of the artery usually at the site of access requiring surgical repair. Conclusion is defined as total obstruction of blood vessel usually due to the thrombus formation dissection or other mechanisms usually at the site of access of plaque pulse or Doppler signal and associated with sign and symptoms of an ischemic limb requiring surgical intervention.

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